

SCOBench: Streaming Continuous Optimisation Benchmark

Supplementary Materials

1 SCOBench

Table 1 provides a detailed description of the benchmark configuration parameters, including default values and parameter ranges.

Table 1: Benchmark configuration Settings

Config param	Default	Range	Description
Seed	-	-	Seed.
Verbose	2	0: None, 1: limited, 2: all details	Details to print.
Optimum Similarity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Max distance in optimum normalised optimum space from reference instance.
Feature Similarity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Max distance in optimum normalised feature space from reference instance.
Trajectory Similarity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Max distance in optimum normalised trajectory space from reference instance.
Max Instance Generation	100	[1, int limit]	Number of instances used in the search for the next instance.
Use Opt Sim	TRUE	True/False	Using Optimum Similarity.
Optimum Transform	random	random/shift	Type of optimum transformation: random: search, shift: shift optimum to within region.
Features	ELA	ELA	Type of features used for feature similarity (by default, only ELA is available).
Number of Feature Calculations	5	[1, int limit]	Number of times features are calculated.
Feature Sample Size	50*dim	-	Size of the samples used for feature generation.
Feature Similarity Method	cosine	cosine/pearson/spearman	Method used to compare feature vectors.
Trajectory Method	current	current/best-so-far	Trajectory method
Trajectory Similarity Method	cosine	cosine/pearson/spearman	Method used to compare trajectory time series.
Similarity Weight	0.5	[0, 1]	Weight for feature and trajectory similarity.
Recurrent Drift Type	1	0/1	0: major or minor drift is applied from the recurrent reference instance. 1: major or minor drift is applied from the previous drifted instance towards the recurrent reference. Default: 1.
Major Drift Opt Severity	0.8	[0.0, 1.0]	Major drift optimum severity.
Major Drift Feature Severity	0.8	[0.0, 1.0]	Major drift feature severity.
Major Drift Trajectory Severity	0.8	[0.0, 1.0]	Major drift trajectory severity.
Re-Major Drift Opt Severity	0.8	[0.0, 1.0]	Re-Major drift optimum severity.
Re-Major Drift Feature Severity	0.8	[0.0, 1.0]	Re-Major drift feature severity.
Re-Major Drift Trajectory Severity	0.8	[0.0, 1.0]	Re-Major drift trajectory severity.
Minor Drift Opt Severity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Minor drift optimum severity.
Minor Drift Feature Severity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Minor drift feature severity.
Minor Drift Trajectory Severity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Minor drift trajectory severity.
Re-Minor Drift Opt Severity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Re-Minor drift optimum severity.
Re-Minor Drift Feature Severity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Re-Minor drift feature severity.
Re-Minor Drift Trajectory Severity	0.2	[0.0, 1.0]	Re-Minor drift trajectory severity.
Major Drift MA Weight Change	0.4	[0.0, 1.0]	Automatic MA weight change during (Re)Major drift.
Minor Drift MA Weight Change	0.05	[0.0, 1.0]	Automatic MA weight change during (Re)Minor drift.

1.1 Stream generation verification

Instance generation budget : As noted in Section 3 of the main paper, generation of a new instance with the required drift takes place according to Algorithm 1. A key parameter of this method is the budget allocated to finding an instance (i.e., the parameter *max_instance_gen*). In order to evaluate the rate S of finding an instance with the exact required similarity, we generate streams from 20 function pairs with 5 seeds each, in dimension 10, using the ordered pairs of the last functions in each BBOB function category (to include a diverse set of functions) with drift pattern of [N, N, Mj, RMj, Mn, RMn, Mn, N, Mj, RMj, Mj, N, Mn, RMn, Mn, Mn, Mn, Mj, N, N] (this pattern contains all drift types from the benchmark, creating a stream with sudden, recurrent, and noisy incremental drift) and calculate S as the number of times the algorithm terminates with generation of an instance in the exact similarities. For the cases in which an exact instance is not found, we record the normalised distance of the generated instance with the smallest weighted deviation from the target similarity threshold.

Thresholds for drift bands : The parameters defining the ‘major’ and ‘minor’ drift bands also affect instance search results. We conduct experiments to understand the impact of these parameters (i.e., the ‘severity’ parameters listed in Table 1) using the drift pattern [N, N, N, N, Mn, Mn, Mn, Mn, Mj, Mj, Mj, Mj] with a search budget (parameter max_instance_gen) of 100. In the first configuration, the base similarity threshold is 0.1, minor drift severity is 0.2, and major drift severity is 0.2. In the second configuration, these values are 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6, respectively. In the third configuration, they are 0.3, 0.6, and 1.0.

2 Results

Table 2: Rate of finding an instance exactly with desired similarity to the reference instance for budgets of 100 and 1000. For instances that fall outside the drift band, we measure the normalised distance to the boundary of the target similarity area .

budget	median exact instances		median feature similarity deviation		median trajectory similarity deviation	
	100	1000	100	1000	100	100
min	50%	55%	0.310	0.148	0.246	0.161
median	50%	72.5%	0.070	0.069	0.165	0.113
max	85%	100%	0.003	0.019	0.053	0.053

Table 3: Rate of finding an exact instance with desired similarity to the reference instance for three similarity thresholds using an instance search budget of 100 (similarity thresholds 1: 0.1, 0.2, 0.2, thresholds 2: 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, thresholds 3: 0.3, 0.6, 1.0). For instances that fall outside the exact drift band, we measure the normalised distance to the boundary of the target similarity area.

thresholds 1	median exact instances	median feature similarity deviation	median trajectory similarity deviation
min	41.67%	0.090000	0.227337
median	66.67%	0.046920	0.115654
max	83.33%	0.013914	0.036278
thresholds 2	median exact instances	median feature similarity deviation	median trajectory similarity deviation
min	33.33%	0.308009	0.447758
median	45.83%	0.115038	0.264402
max	66.67%	0.050727	0.138592
thresholds 3	median exact instances	median feature similarity deviation	median trajectory similarity deviation
min	33.33%	0.207433	0.616111
median	33.33%	0.129678	0.366843
max	50%	0.059619	0.201851

Figure 1: Algorithm performances across 5 seeds, 91 streams, 20 instances per stream, and 30 runs using AOCC. Using drift sequence: N, N, Mj, RMj, Mn, RMn, Mn, N, Mj, RMj, Mj, N, Mn, RMn, Mn, Mn, Mn, Mj, N, N.

Figure 2: Visualisations of the differences in median absolute AOCC compared to the reference instance across all algorithm runs and seeds. The rows are the streams, showing MA-BBOB pairs, while the columns are the instances labelled with the corresponding drift type. The value in each cell corresponds to the algorithm behaviour change normalised across the streams, where lower values indicate similar behaviour to the runs on the reference instance, and higher values indicate different behaviour.

(a) RCoBYLA

(b) modcma

(c) DiagonalCMA

(d) modde

(e) DifferentialEvolution

(f) Combined

Figure 3: Similar to Fig. 2; however, cells are only coloured if the change in algorithm behaviour is statistically different.

Table 2 shows the effect of instance search budget on exact instance finding rate. For search budget of 100, median 50% of instances are exact; however, the rest of the instances have only small deviations from the exact similarity values. Median feature similarity deviation is 0.7, while median trajectory similarity deviation is 0.165. For search budget of 1000, the median exact instance rate is increased to 72.5%, while the median deviations are lowerer; 0.069 and 0.113 respectively.

Table 3 summarises threshold experiments. Results show that the benchmark is able to produce higher instance search performance with lower similarity thresholds. With the first configuration, a median of 66.67% of the instances are within all three target regions. These proportions are decreasing with larger thresholds. The median similarity deviations show that with smaller threshold values, the benchmark is finding better instances, and their deviation from target regions is smaller.

We benchmarked the performance of five algorithms over multiple streams, specifically, RCobyala, DiagonalCMA, DifferentialEvolution from the Nevergrad framework^[1], as well as modular CMA (modcma)^[2] and modular differential evolution (modDE)^[3]. Algorithm runs were repeated 30 times on each instance, recording the anytime performance.

Fig. 2 demonstrates the anytime algorithm performance difference using AOCC compared to the reference instance on streams created from 72 MA-BBOB function pairs. For most algorithms, major and re-major drift results in the largest performance change with the exception of streams containing functions 21 and 22 (x_21 or x_22). For these streams algorithm behaviour change is not dependent on drift. In Fig. 3, cells are only coloured if the anytime performance change of the algorithms is significantly different using the Wilcoxon test and Fisher’s method. Here, the differences between algorithms are more noticeable, as algorithms like RCobyala have significant changes between almost every instance, while DifferentialEvolution mostly contain statistical significant performance changes with major and re-major drifts. Fig. 1 shows the overall performance of the algorithms over all streams. Here, modCMA is shown as the best-performing algorithm.

References

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